

The Disadvantages are Discussed along with a Summary of Engineering Bearing types and uses

¹Abdulrahman Yusuf Abdullahi, ²Umar Farouk Musa, ³Firuze AK, ⁴Muhammad Ahmad Baballe*

¹Department of Electrical Engineering, Kano University of Science and Technology Wudil, Kano Nigeria.

²Department of Architecture Technology, School of Environment Studies Gwarzo, Kano State Polytechnic, Nigeria.

³Research Scholar, Guwahati university, India.

⁴Department of Mechatronics Engineering, Nigerian Defence Academy (NDA), Kaduna, Nigeria.

*Corresponding author: [Muhammad Ahmad Baballe](#)

Department of Mechatronics Engineering, Nigerian Defence Academy (NDA), Kaduna, Nigeria.

ORCID: 0000-0001-9441-7023

Abstract

This comprehensive study looks at the evolution, guiding concepts, types, applications, challenges, and recent advancements in bearings in engineering contexts. From prehistoric societies to the industrial revolution, bearing development may be traced back through time, including significant inventions that shaped modern engineering methods. Fundamental principles provide clarity on key concepts for optimizing bearing performance, including load distribution, friction reduction, and lubrication. A range of bearing types, from complex fluid and magnetic bearings to traditional ball and roller bearings, that exhibit versatility in engineering applications are examined. Innovation is driven by advancements in materials and production techniques, like ceramics, polymers, and additive manufacturing, which enhance the performance and sustainability of bearings. Opportunities for preventative maintenance and increased operational effectiveness are presented by new advancements in sensor technology and smart bearings. The disadvantages are discussed along with a summary of engineering bearing types and uses.

Keywords: Disadvantages, Bearings, Applications, Types, Impacts.

I. INTRODUCTION

Among the many different engineering applications, bearings are essential parts. They lessen frictional forces and contribute to efficient and smooth mobility. Numerous industries, including the automotive, aerospace, industrial, and construction sectors, use these mechanical devices. It is crucial for engineers and designers to comprehend the fundamentals, varieties, and uses of bearings if they are to maximize mechanical systems and machines. Basic bearings were used to lessen friction between moving parts in ancient societies, which is where bearings first appeared. According to historical records, the ancient Egyptians and Romans used crude bearing arrangements that were lubricated with oils or greases produced from animal fats and constructed of wood, stone, or metal. A number of important turning points in the history of bearings were reached during the Renaissance, most notably the inclusion of primitive ball bearings in Leonardo da Vinci's drawings and designs. But it wasn't until the 18th and 19th centuries' Industrial Revolution—driven by the growing needs of mechanized industries—that bearings saw significant developments. The design of machinery was altered by inventions like the modern ball bearing, which was created in the late 18th century by Welsh inventor Philip Vaughan. They cleared the path for further developments in bearing technology [1]. Bearings act as pivotal components within mechanical systems by providing support, reducing friction, and facilitating controlled motion between two or more moving parts. At its core, a bearing comprises two essential elements: an outer race (housing) and an inner race (shaft), with rolling elements such as balls, rollers, or needles situated between them. These rolling elements effectively distribute loads, enabling smooth rotation or linear motion with minimal resistance. Bearings are utilized across most engineering disciplines, each with specific types tailored to suit diverse operational requirements. In mechanical and automotive engineering, for instance, ball bearings find extensive application in wheel assemblies, gearboxes, and electric motors due to their low friction and high efficiency characteristics. Similarly, roller bearings are

avored in heavy-duty applications such as conveyor systems, cranes, and industrial machinery, where robustness and load-carrying capacity are paramount. Moreover, advanced materials and manufacturing techniques have facilitated the development of specialized bearings engineered to withstand extreme conditions and operating environments. Ceramic bearings, for instance, exhibit exceptional resistance to corrosion, high temperatures, and wear, making them ideal for aerospace, marine, and high-speed applications. Bearings epitomize the symbiotic relationship between engineering innovation and practical utility, serving as silent enablers of modern civilization's mechanical infrastructure. As technology evolves, the quest for superior bearing solutions continues, driving research and development efforts to enhance performance, longevity, and sustainability across diverse industrial sectors [2].

Figure 1: Historical sketches of ball, roller, and taper bearings devised by Leonardo da Vinci

II. RELATED WORKS

Bearings are essential parts of engineering systems and are necessary to provide effective motion with the least amount of friction. Their importance is felt in many sectors, such as manufacturing, construction, aerospace, and automotive, where dependability and accurate motion control are critical. Bearings are essentially the silent enablers of the mechanical backbone of contemporary civilization, supporting the operation of myriad machines and mechanical systems. Because they can sustain rotating or oscillating components, bearings are essential in engineering because they lessen wear and friction between moving parts [1]. Bearings contribute to increased energy efficiency, longer equipment lifespans, and better mechanical system performance by carrying out this crucial job [3]. Furthermore, bearings are essential for reducing the negative effects of dynamic loads and vibrations, which guarantees the steady and smooth operation of machinery under a variety of operating circumstances [4]. An extensive summary of bearings, including kinds, functions, and technical applications, is given in this literature study. This review provides insights into the fundamental principles regulating bearing operation and the most recent innovations in bearing technology by combining existing research findings, industry best practices, and historical events. This overview also looks at the various ways that bearings are used in various engineering fields, emphasizing how they can improve machinery performance, increase reliability, and promote creativity.

2.1 Historical Evolution of Bearings

- a) **Ancient Origins and Early Developments:** The earliest bearings were used to lessen friction between moving parts in ancient societies, which is where bearing technology first emerged. According to historical evidence, simple bearing arrangements composed of metal, stone, or wood and lubricated with oils or greases generated from animal fats were used by civilizations like the Romans and Egyptians [5]. The smoother operation of machinery and mechanical equipment made possible by these early bearings laid the groundwork for later developments in bearing technology.
- b) **Key Milestones in Bearing Technology:** Throughout history, the development of bearings has seen major turning points, with noteworthy breakthroughs signifying important phases in the improvement of engineering. During the Renaissance, notable advancements in bearing design and innovation were accomplished by innovative inventors

and engineers, marking one such milestone. Early knowledge of the advantages of rolling parts in lowering friction and promoting motion can be seen in Leonardo da Vinci's drawings and plans, which included crude ball bearings [6]. But the needs of mechanized industries didn't cause bearing technology to undergo a paradigm shift until the industrial revolution of the 18th and 19th centuries.

- c) **Impact of the Industrial Revolution on Bearing Advancements:** The Industrial Revolution changed the face of engineering and manufacturing and ushered in a new age of creativity and technological growth. Reliable and effective bearing solutions were required throughout this time due to the increased automation of industries to support the expanding range of mechanical systems and machines. The design of machinery was altered by inventions like the modern ball bearing, which was created in the late 18th century by Welsh inventor Philip Vaughan. They cleared the path for further developments in bearing technology [1]. Precision machining methods and standardized manufacturing procedures were introduced, which further sped up the production of high-quality bearings and made them widely used in a variety of industrial sectors.

New alloys and metallurgical processes that improve bearing performance and durability were made possible by the industrial revolution, which also fuelled advances in material science. These developments, along with enhancements in sealing and lubrication technologies, led to the widespread use of bearings in a variety of technical applications, ranging from steam engines and textile mills to industrial machinery and railroad locomotives [7].

2.2 Fundamental Principles of Bearings

2.2.1 Definition and Basic Components of Bearings

By lowering friction and sustaining loads, bearings are mechanical devices that enable controlled and smooth motion between two or more moving elements. Fundamentally, bearings are made up of two races: an inner race (shaft) and an outer race (housing), with rolling parts like rollers, balls, or needles positioned in between. These rolling parts provide for low resistance linear motion or smooth rotation by evenly distributing loads [8].

2.2.2 Types of Loads and Their Effects on Bearings

Bearings are subjected to various types of loads during operation, including radial, axial, and moment loads. Radial loads act perpendicular to the axis of rotation and are common in applications where rotational motion is required, such as wheels and pulleys. On the other hand, axial loads act parallel to the rotation axis and are typically encountered in thrust applications, such as gearboxes and thrust bearings. Moment loads result from forces that create bending or twisting moments on the bearing, often seen in applications involving shaft misalignment or angular motion. The effects of these loads on bearings can vary depending on factors such as load magnitude, direction, and distribution, impacting bearing performance, lifespan, and reliability [9].

2.2.3 Principles of Friction, Lubrication, and Wear in Bearing Operation

Friction, lubrication, and wear are fundamental aspects of bearing operation that significantly influence performance and longevity. Frictional forces arise between the contacting surfaces of the bearing components during motion, resulting in energy loss and wear over time. Proper lubrication is critical in minimizing friction and wear by forming a thin film between the bearing surfaces, reducing direct metal-to-metal contact, and dissipating heat generated during operation. Lubricants such as oils, greases, and solid lubricants are selected based on operating conditions, load requirements, and environmental considerations. Additionally, wear in bearings can occur due to contamination, inadequate lubrication, or excessive loads, leading to premature failure and performance degradation [10].

2.2 Types of Bearings

Figure 2: Types of Bearings

2.3.1 Ball Bearings:

Ball bearings are one of the most common types of bearings. They use spherical balls to facilitate smooth rotational motion between two surfaces. These bearings are widely employed in various applications due to their high efficiency, low friction, and capability to support radial and axial loads. Ball bearings come in different configurations, including deep groove, angular contact, and thrust ball bearings, each designed to accommodate specific load and speed requirements [11].

2.3.2 Roller Bearings:

Roller bearings utilize cylindrical or tapered rollers instead of balls to support loads and reduce friction between moving parts. This category encompasses several subtypes, including cylindrical, tapered, and spherical roller bearings. Cylindrical roller bearings are well-suited for applications with high radial loads. In contrast, tapered roller bearings handle radial and axial loads, making them ideal for automotive and heavy machinery applications. On the other hand, spherical roller bearings are designed to accommodate misalignment and heavy axial loads in harsh operating conditions [12].

2.3.3 Thrust Bearings:

Thrust bearings are engineered to support axial loads, allowing for controlled motion along the axis of rotation. These bearings come in various designs, including ball thrust bearings, roller thrust bearings, and fluid thrust bearings. Ball thrust bearings utilize ball bearings arranged in a raceway to support axial loads, while roller thrust bearings employ cylindrical or tapered rollers for the same purpose. Fluid thrust bearings, such as hydrostatic and hydrodynamic thrust bearings, rely on fluid film lubrication to support axial loads and smoothly operate in high-speed applications [13].

2.3.4 Plain Bearings:

Plain bearings, also known as bushings or sleeve bearings, consist of a cylindrical surface with no rolling elements. They rely on sliding motion between surfaces to support loads. These bearings are commonly used in applications where low friction and noise levels are critical, such as pumps, compressors, and agricultural machinery. Journal bearings, which support radial loads, and sleeve bearings, which support axial loads, are two common types of plain bearings utilized in engineering systems [14].

2.3.5 Fluid Bearings:

Fluid bearings utilize a thin fluid film, typically oil or air, to support loads and facilitate motion between surfaces. These bearings operate on hydrostatic or hydrodynamic lubrication principles, where pressurized fluid creates a film that separates the bearing surfaces. Hydrostatic bearings rely on external pumps to supply pressurized fluid to the bearing, while hydrodynamic bearings generate the necessary fluid film through relative motion between surfaces. Fluid bearings offer high load capacity, low friction, and quiet operation, making them suitable for high-speed and precision applications [15].

2.3.6 Magnetic Bearings:

Magnetic bearings employ magnetic fields to levitate and support rotating or oscillating components without physical contact, eliminating the need for traditional bearing components such as rolling elements and lubricants. These bearings utilize electromagnetic forces to maintain stable positioning and control motion, offering benefits such as low friction, high precision, and maintenance-free operation. Magnetic bearings find applications in various industries, including aerospace, turbomachinery, and high-speed rotational systems [16].

2.4 Materials and Manufacturing Techniques

2.4.1 Common Materials Used in Bearing Construction:

Traditionally, bearings have been predominantly manufactured using steel due to its excellent strength, durability, and machinability. High-carbon chromium bearing steels, such as AISI 52100, are commonly employed for bearing races and rolling elements due to their high hardness, wear resistance, and fatigue strength. Other materials used in bearing construction include stainless steels for corrosion resistance and non-ferrous metals such as bronze and brass for specialized applications requiring self-lubricating properties or high-temperature resistance [17].

2.4.2 Advances in Bearing Materials:

Recent advancements in materials science have led to the development of novel bearing materials with enhanced performance characteristics. Ceramics, such as silicon nitride (Si₃N₄) and zirconia (ZrO₂), offer advantages such as superior hardness, corrosion resistance, and thermal stability compared to traditional steel bearings. These ceramic bearings exhibit reduced friction, extended lifespan, and suitability for high-speed and high-temperature applications, making them ideal for demanding environments in aerospace, automotive, and medical industries [18]. Furthermore,

polymers and composite materials have emerged as viable alternatives for bearing applications, offering lightweight construction, corrosion resistance, and damping properties. Polymer bearings, composed of materials such as polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) and polyetheretherketone (PEEK), find applications in industries requiring non-metallic, self-lubricating, and maintenance-free bearing solutions [19].

2.4.3 Manufacturing Processes for Bearings:

Manufacturing processes for bearings encompass a range of techniques tailored to meet specific design requirements and performance criteria. Machining processes, such as turning, milling, and grinding, are commonly employed to fabricate bearing components with tight tolerances and precise geometries. Forging processes involve deformation metal blanks under high pressure and temperature to produce components with improved mechanical properties and grain structure. Casting techniques, including investment and sand casting, are utilized to manufacture complex-shaped bearing components in large quantities with cost-effective production [20]. Additionally, additive manufacturing (3D printing) advancements have enabled the fabrication of custom-designed bearings with intricate geometries and optimized material properties, offering flexibility and agility in bearing production [21].

2.5 Applications of Bearings in Engineering

2.5.1 Automotive Industry:

Bearings play a crucial role in various automotive applications, contributing to vehicle smooth and reliable operation. In automotive engines, bearings support rotating components such as crankshafts, camshafts, and connecting rods, enabling efficient power transmission and minimizing frictional losses. Wheel bearings facilitate the smooth rotation of wheels and ensure vehicle stability and handling. Additionally, transmission systems rely on bearings to support gears and shafts, facilitating gear shifting and power transfer. Bearings in automotive applications are subjected to high loads, speeds, and temperature variations, necessitating robust designs and materials [22].

2.5.2 Aerospace Industry:

The aerospace industry relies on bearings for critical aircraft, spacecraft, and aerospace systems applications. Bearings in aerospace applications are subjected to extreme conditions, including high speeds, temperatures, and vibrations while maintaining stringent requirements for reliability and performance. In aircraft engines, bearings support rotating components such as turbine blades, compressor rotors, and gearbox shafts, ensuring smooth and efficient operation. Bearings are also utilized in landing gear systems, control surfaces, and actuators, contributing to the safety and functionality of aerospace platforms [23].

2.5.3 Industrial Machinery:

Industrial machinery encompasses various applications, from manufacturing and processing equipment to material handling and automation systems, which rely on bearings for smooth and precise motion control. Bearings in industrial machinery support rotating shafts, spindles, and rollers in equipment such as pumps, compressors, conveyors, and machine tools. These bearings are designed to withstand heavy loads, high speeds, and continuous operation while maintaining accuracy and reliability in demanding industrial environments [24].

2.5.4 Construction and Infrastructure:

The construction and infrastructure sectors utilize bearings in various applications to support structural components, facilitate movement, and mitigate vibrations. Bearings are employed in bridge bearings, expansion joints, and seismic isolation systems to accommodate thermal expansion, movement, and dynamic loads, ensuring structural integrity and resilience. In construction machinery such as cranes, excavators, and concrete pumps, bearings support rotating components and facilitate smooth operation under heavy loads and harsh conditions [25].

2.5.5 Robotics and Automation:

Bearings play a vital role in robotics and automation systems, enabling precise motion control, accuracy, and repeatability in robotic manipulators, CNC machines, and automated assembly lines. Bearings support robot joints and actuators, allowing for smooth and coordinated movement in multiple axes. Additionally, bearings are used in linear motion systems, rotary stages, and gantry systems to facilitate linear and rotational motion with minimal friction and backlash. In robotics and automation, bearings contribute to improved productivity, efficiency, and flexibility in manufacturing and assembly operations [26].

2.6 Challenges and Emerging Trends

2.6.1 Challenges in Bearing Design, Performance, and Maintenance:

Despite advancements in bearing technology, several challenges persist in bearing design, performance, and maintenance. One significant challenge is the demand for bearings to operate under increasingly demanding conditions, including higher speeds, heavier loads, and harsher environments. This necessitates continuous innovation in bearing

materials, lubrication systems, and sealing technologies to enhance performance and reliability [27]. Moreover, the trend towards miniaturization and lightweight design poses challenges in maintaining bearing durability and load-carrying capacity while reducing size and weight. Additionally, challenges related to bearing fatigue, wear, and failure modes require ongoing research and development efforts to improve bearing lifespan and mitigate downtime in industrial applications [28].

2.6.2 Emerging Trends in Bearing Technology:

Several emerging trends in bearing technology are shaping the future of the industry. One notable trend is the development of smart bearings equipped with sensors and monitoring systems to provide real-time data on bearing conditions, performance, and health. These smart bearings enable predictive maintenance strategies, allowing for proactive detection of potential failures and optimization of maintenance schedules to minimize downtime and enhance reliability [29]. Another emerging trend is integrating advanced materials, such as ceramics, polymers, and composites, into bearing design to improve performance characteristics such as wear resistance, corrosion resistance, and temperature stability. Furthermore, advancements in additive manufacturing technologies enable the production of complex geometries and customized bearings tailored to specific applications, offering greater flexibility and agility in bearing design and production [30].

2.6.3 Environmental Considerations and Sustainability:

Environmental considerations and sustainability are increasingly important in bearing design and manufacturing processes. Efforts to reduce carbon emissions, energy consumption, and resource usage drive the development of eco-friendly bearing solutions. This includes the adoption of environmentally friendly lubricants, such as bio-based oils and greases, to minimize environmental impact and improve workplace safety [31]. Additionally, enhancing bearing durability and reliability contributes to extended maintenance intervals and reduced waste generated from bearing replacements. Furthermore, initiatives to optimize bearing performance and efficiency support overall energy conservation and environmental stewardship across various industries [32].

III. Disadvantages of bearings in engineering

1. Limited lifespan due to eventual exhaustion.
2. Low capacity to withstand shocks.
3. High initial cost.
4. Coefficient of friction is greater at higher speeds [33].

CONCLUSION

From ancient civilizations to the Industrial Revolution, bearing technology has undergone constant invention and adaptation, which has shaped modern engineering methods and machinery design. This is highlighted by the historical evolution of bearings. The basic principles clarify important ideas that control bearing operation, highlighting the importance of lubrication, load distribution, and friction reduction in maximizing dependability and performance. From conventional ball and roller bearings to sophisticated fluid and magnetic bearings, the taxonomy of bearings reveals a wide variety of bearing types. The diversity and adaptability of bearing technology are demonstrated by the distinct benefits that each type of bearing offers and how it is designed for particular engineering applications. Continuous advancements influencing bearing performance, durability, and sustainability are demonstrated by developments in materials and production processes, such as the use of ceramics, polymers, and additive manufacturing. These advancements help engineering systems become more reliable, more efficient, and less harmful to the environment. Problems like using predictive maintenance techniques and optimizing bearing design for harsh environments point to areas that require more study and creativity. Proactive maintenance and increased operating efficiency are possible with emerging trends like smart bearings, which are made possible by sensor technology and data analytics [34]. There is discussion of the bearing's shortcomings in mechanical engineering.

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